

The thrip attack was quite severe. The average damage score was 6. Of 390 varieties or lines. 21 were resistant, 49 moderately resistant, and 316 susceptible to highly susceptible. The resistant lines were also found moderately resistant to rice whorl maggot.

Cultivars found resistant to thrips were: B707C-MR-13-1 (Remadja//IR22/C₄-63G); IET 3817; IET 4506; IR5624-164-2-1 (IR841-85/IR2061//IR2049/IR2031); IR3264-30-2-3, IR7963-30-4-3, and IR7963-87-3-3

(IR3264-13/IR1702-74-3//IR2055-219-1); IR9129-2-2, IR9129-142-2, IR9129-169-3, and IR9129-393-2 (IR28/IR2053-521-1-1//IR2071-625-1); IR9218-2763 (IR36/IR2053-521-3//IR30); BW 78; MRC 505 (BPI-121-3-I/TKM6); IR2058-78-1-3-2-3 (IR1416-131/IR1364//IR1366/IR1539); CR 1016 (Waikoku/T 90); IR2798-88-3-2 (IR1529-680/IR1913-41//IR1514A-E666; TKM 6; Thirissa; IR4791-80 (IR3342/IR3341); and Kaohsiung Sen Yu 185 (IR1561-152-3/Kaohsiung 2). ■

Rice resistance to whitebacked planthopper

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A mass-screening method identified at AICRIP the cultivar IET6288 as highly resistant to the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath, a major rice pest in northern and central India. IET-6288 is a progeny of the cross PTB18/PTB2//IR8.

To develop high yielding varieties with multiple resistance, IET6288 was

crossed with another high yielding variety, Phalguna, which is resistant to gall midge but susceptible to WBPH. Phalguna is a derivative of the cross IR8/Siam 29. The cross IET6288; Phalguna, designated as RP2149, was screened in the greenhouse. The F₁ plants were resistant to WBPH. The F₂ population had a ratio of 3 resistant to 1 susceptible. To confirm the findings, the F₂ population was screened three times in three separate lots. The same ratio was obtained in all cases (see table). The results show that in this cross, a pair of dominant genes control WHPH resistance. ■

Segregation for resistance to the whitebacked planthopper in the F₂ population of the cross IET6288 (resistant)/Phalguna (susceptible) (RP2149). Hyderabad, India.

Lot	Plants (no.)		X ² (3:1)	P value
	Resistant	Susceptible		
1	57	19	0.00	0.995-1.00
2	112	34	1.29	0.50-0.75
3	306	116	1.31	0.25-0.25
Total	475	169	0.51	0.25-0.50

Relative susceptibility of rice varieties to gall midge under low rainfall conditions

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) has become a regular pest of the main-season (Jul-Nov) rice

1. Rainfall for 1979 and the average for 23 years in Bihar, India. Figures in parentheses are the number of rainy days during the month.

crop in Bihar, particularly in the Chhotanagpur plateau. Rainfall was deficient in 1979 (Fig. 1).

A field study was made of 19 rice cultivars, including two dryland and two rainfed wetland rices. Observations on silver shoot occurrence were recorded (50 hills/variety) in the second week of October — the infestation peak in 1979.

Among the dryland rices RAU40004-105 was most resistant (3.25% silver shoots) (see table). The two cultivars

Reaction of transplanted rice cultivars to gall midge in 1979 kharif, Ranchi, India.

Cultivar	Tillers (no./hill)	Silver shoots ^a (%)
BR10	13.1	0.2 a
BR34	14.2	3.1 b
RAU40004-105	6.6	3.3 bc
BR9	11.5	3.5 bcd
Panidhan	13.7	4.7 bcde
Pankaj	14.2	4.8 bcde
Archana	10.4	5.0 bcde
RAU40004-109	8.0	5.4 cde
RAU4009-3	6.8	6.1 def
IET2895	9.7	6.1 def
RAU4009-17	7.8	6.4 def
RAU4009-15	6.4	9.5 fg
IR26	12.6	12.5 g
BR8	11.1	13.4 g
IR20	12.8	14.2 g
IR30	9.0	15.3 g
Sita	13.5	21.5 h
Jaya	12.1	21.8 h
RAU4009-29	6.0	35.8 i

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

2. Rainfall and gall midge incidence. Ranchi, India.

suiting to rainfed wetland, RAU4009-3 and RAU4009-17, had 6.1 and 6.4% tiller infestation. Of the wetland cultivars, BRI0 was highly resistant (0.2%) (Fig.2). Maximum damage occurred on RAU4009-29 (35.8%), which also had poor tillering (6 tillers/hill). The susceptible variety Jaya had 21.8% silver shoots; the present resistant variety, IET2895, had 6.1%. ■

Honeydew excretion, feeding activity, and insect weight gain as criteria in determining levels of varietal resistance to the green leafhopper

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Studies on the mechanism of rice resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) have used the quantity of honeydew excretion and insect weight gain to determine levels of varietal resistance. These criteria have provided a better assessment of resistance levels than has the seedling bulk screening method. This study was conducted to determine if those parameters could be used to measure the level of resistance to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. The susceptible variety TN1 was compared with the resistant IR29.

One-day-old adults were starved for 4 hours, weighed individually, and placed in parafilm sachets on 30-day-old plants

Each parafilm sachet contained a day-old adult green leafhopper and served as a replication.

(see photo). There were nine replications for each variety; each sachet served as a replication. After 24 hours, the insects were removed and weighed. Honeydew weight was determined by weighing the parafilm sachet with honeydew, then reweighing the sachet after wiping it dry to remove the honeydew.

The weight of the honeydew excreted on TN1 was only 2.5 times that excreted by hoppers feeding on IR29 (see table). But the weight of assimilated food, which is due primarily to weight gain,

provided more accurate information on the levels of resistance of the two varieties. The weight of assimilated food on TN1 was 13 times that on IR29.

As indicated by the amount of honeydew excreted, feeding was also substantial on the resistant IR29, but most of the intake apparently was not assimilated. Measurements of the amount of food ingested and assimilated can be used to detect levels of resistance to GLH. ■

Comparison of ingestion and metabolic utilization of food of the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* feeding on a susceptible and a resistant variety.^a IRRI, 1979.

Variety	Honey dew wt (mg)	Qty of food ingested ^b (mg)	Wt of as-similated food ^c (mg)	Nutritive value ^d
TN1 (Susceptible)	25.587	26.380 a	0.793 a	0.030
IR29 (Resistant)	10.904	10.966 b	0.062 b	0.006

^aMean for 9 insects starved for 4 hours, then fed on 30-day-old plants for 24 hours. In a column, means followed by a different letter are significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^bQty of food ingested = wt assimilated food + wt of honeydew. ^cWt of assimilated food = insect wt gain or loss due to feeding + wt loss due to metabolism. ^dNutritive value = ratio of wt of assimilated food to wt of ingested food.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Morphological studies of rice varieties that are tolerant of and susceptible to submergence as seedlings

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Varietal differences in submergence tolerance at the seedling stage have been reported. The morphological differences

between submergence tolerant and susceptible rice varieties at seedling stage was the objective of this study.

The seedling height measured in 10-day-old seedlings before complete submergence did not show any significant correlation with submergence tolerance. However, the tolerant varieties were generally taller than the susceptible varieties after complete submergence and recovery.

Although there was no significant correlation between the primary leaf length and survival percentage of plants when submerged in water, the tolerant varieties (all traditional) generally had longer primary leaves than the susceptible varieties (which, except for Leb Mue Nahng 111, were all improved varieties).

Table 1 shows the first and second leaf blades were longer in tolerant